

RENEWABLE ENERGY-BASED MOBILE WEATHER UPDATE STATION

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ABSTRACT

Monitoring weather plays a crucial role in human life, making the collection of data on climate changes imperative. This paper aims to develop a weather station to monitor climate parameters in off-grid regions. The project includes sensors for detecting temperature, humidity, rainfall, LPG levels, carbon monoxide, smoke, altitude, and barometric pressure. The Arduino gathers information from the sensors, displays it on an LCD screen, and additionally sends SMS alerts via a GSM module. Accurate weather updates are essential for successful planning in agriculture, fishing, and various other activities. Unfortunately, weather information often lacks accuracy for specific regions, relying instead on data from the nearest weather station. This project calculates and compares the error level between national climate forecasts and actual readings. It is designed to assist individuals in remote and off-grid areas who rely on weather information for their livelihoods.

Keywords: Monitoring The Real-Time Weather Conditions, Renewable Energy, GSM Module.

I. INTRODUCTION

A weather station, whether situated on land or at sea, is equipped with apparatus to assess atmospheric conditions, providing vital information for understanding weather patterns and atmospheric states. It measures various parameters such as temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, wind direction, and precipitation amounts. Measurements are conducted with minimal obstructions for wind readings, while temperature and humidity measurements are shielded from direct exposure to solar radiation or insulation. Manual observations are typically made at least once daily, while automated systems can provide up to twenty-four observations per day. At sea, weather conditions are monitored by ships and buoys, which track metrics like sea surface temperature, humidity, wind speed, and barometric pressure. Personal weather stations, owned and operated by individuals, have become increasingly sophisticated, incorporating various sensors to measure weather conditions. While sensor models may vary, they commonly measure parameters such as temperature, humidity, and precipitation. Weather forecasts play a crucial role in daily life, particularly in sectors like agriculture, where crop production activities are heavily influenced by weather conditions such as temperature, humidity, rainfall, dew point, and barometric pressure. In regions like Bangladesh, where agriculture is a vital part of the economy and many people live in rural or coastal areas without access to electricity or official weather stations, accurate weather information is essential for planning and decision-making. However, existing weather reports often lack accuracy for specific regions, as they rely on data from centralized weather stations. This project aims to address this gap by establishing a network of weather stations to collect local climate data. By deploying weather stations in remote and off-grid areas, it will provide accurate and timely weather information to support livelihoods and decision-making. The proposed weather station will measure parameters such as temperature, humidity, rainfall, and barometric pressure, as well as additional factors like dew point, LPG, carbon monoxide (CO), and smoke in the air. These readings will be transmitted to users' mobile phones and displayed for easy access and interpretation.

II. METHODOLOGY

This project deals with weather information. A weather station provides so many data. Temperature, Humidity, Raindrop, Altitude and Barometric pressure are covered in this project. The measurements taken include temperature, humidity, raindrop, water level and barometric pressure. When the sensors sense the data from the weather then it will be automatically displayed on the LCD display.

In this section, the equipment which were used in this project are briefly discussed and their work function and their features. In this chapter, circuit modeling and designing plans of “renewable powdered portable Weather update station” will be discussed. The Arduino sends the data both LCD and GSM at a time and GSM analysis the data, after analyzing the data it sends the message into mobile. The Hardware implementation was performed on the perspectives of project goal and the whole system is described with the help of respecting software (Proteus 8.5, Arduino 1.6.7). The working process of the project is also discussed in this section. The main equipment for to complete the project were:

- Arduino MEGA
- GSM
- Humidity & Temperature Sensor (DHT22)
- Barometer Sensor (BMP180)
- Raindrop Module (MH-RD)
- Gas detecting sensor (MQ2)
- LCD
- PV Panel
- Charge Controller
- Lead acid Battery

2.1 Circuit Designing and Simulation

Before hardware implementation, circuits required for this project are designed and simulated to check whether the system works or not. There are various ways of programming using different kinds of software. Each software has different types of programming tasks.

As we used Arduino MEGA in our project, Arduino software is our required software. Because it allows the software by which Arduino MEGA can be programmed to do the tasks. Arduino software comes up with different types of version depending on the operating system, database and firmware. Among the different versions Windows version of Arduino 1.6.7 was the ideal choice to program.

To design the schematic diagrams and simulation “Proteus Design Suite version 8.5” was used. As “Proteus Design Suite version 8.5” has inbuilt library for Arduino MEGA, it was the best choice for conducting simulation. To program the Arduino MEGA, hex files were created using the Arduino software and then the code was compiled in the Arduino MEGA.

2.2 Working Principle

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Solar powered portable weather update station

From the diagram, the working process of the project can be described easily. There are three sides- input side and output side and intermediate state of the diagram for detecting the weather. The input side consisted of DHT-22, Raindrop module, Gas detecting sensor, Barometric pressure sensor. One LCD on the output side. And another side is called intermediate state. In intermediate state 2 things are here, one is Arduino MEGA and another one is GSM.

At the beginning the sensors are sensing the temperature, humidity, is raining or not, LPG gas, Carbon mono-oxide, smoke, Altitude barometric pressure from the environment. All the information or data transfer to the Arduino which are taken from the environment by the sensor. Arduino receives the data and send it to the LCD. All the values will be displayed in the LCD. If any person wants to know the actual condition of weather, then he or she can send a message to GSM what is displayed on LCD at that moment, these data are transferred to GSM by Arduino. After getting the data from Arduino, GSM sends it to the consumer through SMS.

The required power to drive the whole circuit is supplied by a solar panel. A solar panel, charge controller, battery and converter are used for the power supply. The LCD monitor displayed the received values of the Arduino MEGA. From the following flow chart, we could understand the process more easily.

Figure 2: Flow chart of the project operation

2.3 Circuit Diagram

Figure 3: Circuit Diagram of Weather Station
III. MODELING AND ANALYSIS

Main Implemented Circuit

The main implemented circuit for weather box is given below:

Figure 4: Main Project Circuitry

To implemented whole circuitry one Arduino MEGA, one temperature and humidity sensor, one barometric pressure sensor, one raindrops module, one LPG, CO (Carbon mono-oxide) & smoke sensor, one GSM module and one LCD display has been used. The required power to run this project, a solar panel is used. The power will be delivered from the solar panel.

The main circuit which is given above is divided into three parts:

- Input side
- Sensors are connected to an Arduino
- Output side
- GSM and LCD display are connected to an Arduino

- Power part
- Arduino and GSM are connected with Battery.

Input side

The input side four sensors are connected with Arduino MEGA. The BMP 180 sensor powered by 3.3V. The BMP180 supports I2C interface and therefore the SDA and SCL pins go to SDA and SCL pins of the Arduino board and the Vin is connected 3.5V pin of Arduino board. Raindrop module has two output pin Analog output pin A0 and digital output pin D0. Analog output pin connected with Arduino A0 pin. Carbon mono-oxide detecting sensor Analog output pin is connected with A3 pin of Arduino board. Temperature and Humidity sensor DHT22 output pin is connected with digital pin 7 These three sensors are powered by 5V which is connected with 5V pin of the Arduino board.

Figure 5: Input side circuitry

Output side

One LCD display and one GSM module are connected with Arduino MEGA. This Portion is named output side. The output is taken by display and GSM.

LCD Display and Arduino MEGA connection

In output side one 20*4 LCD display is connected with Arduino MEGA. The seven Digital Pins of Arduino MEGA is connected to the LCD module were,

- Arduino D3 ↔ RS pin of LCD
- Arduino D2 ↔ En1 pin of LCD
- Arduino D10 ↔ En2 pin of LCD
- Arduino D5 ↔ D12 pin of LCD
- Arduino D4 ↔ D13 pin of LCD
- Arduino D9 ↔ D14 pin of LCD
- Arduino D8 ↔ D15 pin of LCD

Display and Arduino MEGA connection is given below:

Figure 6: Display Output side circuitry

GSM and Arduino connection

In output side a GSM (Global System for Mobile communications) is also connected with Arduino MEGA. Digital pin D7 of Arduino MEGA is connected to the TX pin of GSM module and digital pin D8 of Arduino MEGA to the RX pin of GSM module. Here, GSM module is used for sending message to the Consumer.

The GSM connection with Arduino MEGA is given below:

Figure 7: GSM output side circuitry

Power part

The required power to run this project, a solar panel is used. The power will be delivered from the solar panel. For this circuit required voltage is 7 to 12 V and minimum current is needed 2A. A solar Panel is connected to the charge controller. Connected with two of Charge controller positive and negative pins with the battery positive and negative pin respectively. Using controller battery charged up preciously.

The battery, charge controller and Solar panel connection below:

Figure 8: Power part circuitry

All the circuitry of weather update device is placed in box for make it more comfortable to carry anywhere.

Figure 9: Complete hardware setup of portable weather update device

Output using Display

Here we used 40*4 LCD display. Display shown weather data using Arduino output.

Weather updates taken by display is given below:

Figure 10: Weather report in LCD Display

Rain drop sensor detect either there is any rain or not. It can be used as a switch. Rain drop module has a rain board and a control board. When dropping a little amount of rain in the rain board, DO output become low. In this time the switch indicator will turn on and the display shown rain detected.

Weather updates taken by display when raining is given below:

Figure 11: Rain detection

Output using GSM

The report is sent to the consumer using GSM. GSM has two pin which is connected with Arduino MEGA. To know weather report, consumer send a message to the GSM. A SIM card is mounted GSM which receiving command by message from any mobile phone. GSM transferred this message to the Arduino MEGA via TX pin. Then Arduino sends output, which is shown in display. GSM received Arduino output by using RX pin. Then GSM SIM card sends

Arduino output to the consumer. Getting weather report using GSM is given below:

Figure 12: Weather report taken by GSM module

Figure 13: SMS obtained from GSM module

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Result and Analysis

Power Calculation

To run Arduino and GSM required continuous powered supply otherwise the system will not work continuously. So, Power supply is a very important portion. Here used a rechargeable battery with a solar panel. Battery will be charged by using solar panel via charge controller. If power is disconnected of GSM then needs to restart.

Solar Panel Rating and Current Calculation

In this project we used a Solar panel. The rating of Solar panel is given the below:

Table 1: Solar Panel rating

Solar panel	Power = 20 W	Current
	Voltage = 13.5 V	$I=20/13.5=1.48$ A
Solar Panel of 20W can generate 1.48 A Current		

Time required to charge battery from solar panel

A Lead Acid battery is used to supply power to run the " Renewable powered portable weather update station". Battery Specification and calculation is given the below table:

Table 2: Charging Time of Battery

Let, Battery capacity 70 % is used and 30% is remaining. Remaining 30% to be charged, required current is $=7.5*30\%= 2.25$ AH.
Time required to charge battery from solar panel $=\text{Required Current to charge the Battery}/\text{Solar panel generating current}$ $=2.25 \text{ AH}/1.48\text{A}$ $=1.52 \text{ H}$ $=1 \text{ Hour } 31 \text{ min}$ Time Required to Charge the Battery from Solar Panel > 1 Hour 31 min.

Current consumptions

The current consumption of this devices is given below

Table 3: Current Consumption of this device

Device Name	Voltage Consumption	Current Consumption
DHT22 Sensor	V= 5 V	I = 2.5 mA
BMP180	V=3.3 V	I= 0.005 mA
Raindrop Sensor	V=5 V	I= 15 mA
MQ2	V=5 V	I=20 mA
Arduino MEGA	V=5 V	I= 400 mA
GSM SIM900	V= 5V	I= 1.5 A
Total consumption of current by our Device = 1.918 A		

Run time

If Battery is fully charged, then the run time of battery calculation is given below.

Table 4: Run time of Battery

From Battery, I=2 AH	Total current consumption of our device, I= 1.918 A
Battery Runtime =7.5/1.918 = 3,91hour Battery Runtime =3.91 hour or 3 hour 54 minutes.	

Data analysis

Taken Data: 03-03-2024

Table 5: Data Table of experimental place

Weather parameter	Measured Data (Shamoly)
Temperature	26.20 C
Humidity	99.90%
LPG	71ppm
CO	2018ppm
Smoke	429ppm
Altitude	68 meters
Barometric Pressure	30562 Pa

Weather and climate information is very important for all over the world. In this case it has a great importance of a weather station. By using proposed weather station, the weather condition can be accurately known. The proposed system is a portable system, so it can be easily moved to any place. It is easy to install and cost effective as well. To run this station, solar power has been used, so that it can be used in off-grid area. A GSM module will help consumer to get the data easily. For this weather station the devices require Arduino MEGA, the sensors and GSM which are economic, efficient and easily adaptable. For using Lead Acid battery, the weight of the station is slightly increased. To minimize weight better battery can be used. To develop this station better equipment can be used but the trade-off here is that retrenchment of overall cost of the whole project. Instead of GSM RF module can be used. For that overall cost will be reduced, but for long range getting the output will be difficult. So, GSM communication method makes our proposed system a better option. So, comparing the cost effectiveness and performance, we found our proposed system is better and appropriate for our country.

V. CONCLUSION

Weather data sensor senses the data from the atmosphere. In this project DHT22 temperature humidity sensor have 5% accuracy in humidity reading and (+_2) in temperature reading. BMP180 (Barometric Pressure Sensor) have (+_10) mb (millibar) accuracy. Rain detector sensor has been used so amount of rain cannot be detected. It only detected it is raining or not. LCD connection part is a sensitive part. Physical hazard may destroy the connection. In GSM a send to get the output put SMS from the GSM module. In power section 12v solar panel is used. It is a comparatively large area consuming to the overall project. Lead acid battery is used that

VI. REFERENCES

[1] Forecasting.", ". (2018). Weather Forecasting. Retrieved from <https://www.encyclopedia.com/earth-and-environment/atmosphere-and-weather/weather-and-climate-terms-and-concepts/weather-0>

[2] Glahn, Harry R., and Dale A. Lowry. "The use of model output statistics (MOS) in objective weather forecasting." Journal of applied meteorology 11, no. 8 (1972): 1203-1211.

[3] Weather forecasting through the ages (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://earthobservatory.nasa.gov/Features/WxForecasting/wx2.php>

- [4] Fuentes, M., M. Vivar, J. M. Burgos, J. Aguilera, and J. A. Vacas. "Design of an accurate, low-cost autonomous data logger for PV system monitoring using Arduino™ that complies with IEC standards." *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 130 (2014): 529-543.
- [5] Davey, Christopher A., and Roger A. Pielke Sr. "Microclimate exposures of surface-based weather stations: Implications for the assessment of long-term temperature trends." *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 86, no. 4 (2005): 497-504.
- [6] Benganem, M. "A low cost wireless data acquisition system for weather station monitoring." (2010).
- [7] What is an Arduino? (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://learn.sparkfun.com/tutorials/what-is-an-arduino>
- [8] Arduino Mega 2560. (n.d.). Retrieved from https://wiki.eprolabs.com/index.php?title=Arduino_Mega_2560 .
- [9] Robokart Arduino Mega 2560 R3 Keypad Kit. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://robokart.com/product/detail?id=22>
- [10] Industries, A. (n.d.). Arduino Mega 2560 R3 (Atmega2560 - assembled). Retrieved from <https://www.adafruit.com/product/191>
- [11] Arduino Mega2560 R3 pinouts photo. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://forum.arduino.cc/index.php?topic=125908.0>
- [12] Arduino - ArduinoBoardMega. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.arduino.cc/en/Main/arduinoBoardMega/>
- [13] Introduction to Arduino Mega 2560. (2018, June 30). Retrieved from <https://www.theengineeringprojects.com/2018/06/introduction-to-arduino-mega-2560.html>
- [14] Arduino Mega Tutorial - Pinout and Schematics. Mega 2560 Specifications. (2018, February 08). Retrieved from <http://www.circuitstoday.com/arduino-mega-pinout-schematics>
- [15] An Easier Electronic Circuit Design Experience. (n.d.). Retrieved from [https://easyeda.com/search?wd=Arduino Mega 2560 schematic](https://easyeda.com/search?wd=Arduino+Mega+2560+schematic)
- [16] Ellis, Trevor M., R. Barry Bousfield, Lucy A. Bissett, Kitman C. Dyrting, Geraldine SM Luk, S. T. Tsim, Katharine Sturm-Ramirez, Robert G. Webster, Yi Guan, and JS Malik Peiris. "Investigation of outbreaks of highly pathogenic H5N1 avian influenza in waterfowl and wild birds in Hong Kong in late 2002." *Avian Pathology* 33, no. 5 (2004): 492-505.
- [17] MUKHTAR, MOHD. "Variations in the read-range of RFID with soils." *Variations* 3, no. 2 (2016).
- [18] Govindaraj, K., G. Vikneshwaran, K. Karthick, and P. Tamilamban. "Enhanced Accident Prevention System in Underground Collieries Using Lab view." *International Journal of Engineering Science Invention*, Salem, India, www.ijesi.org 2, no. 11.
- [19] Shibata, Hideo, Masahiro Ito, Masahiro Asakursa, and Kenzo Watanabe. "A digital hygrometer using a polyimide film relative humidity sensor." *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* 45, no. 2 (1996): 564-569.
- [20] Kaewmard, Nattapol, and Saiyan Saiyod. "Sensor data collection and irrigation control on vegetable crop using smart phone and wireless sensor networks for smart farm." In *Wireless Sensors (ICWiSE), 2014 IEEE Conference on*, pp. 106-112. IEEE, 2014.
- [21] Trilles, Sergio, Alejandro Luján, Óscar Belmonte, Raúl Montoliu, Joaquín Torres-Sospedra, and Joaquín Huerta. "SEnviro: a sensorized platform proposal using open hardware and open standards." *Sensors* 15, no. 3 (2015): 5555-5582.
- [22] Schofield, Kenneth, Mark L. Larson, and Keith J. Vadas. "Vehicle rain sensor using imaging sensor." U.S. Patent 6,320,176, issued November 20, 2001.
- [23] B. (n.d.). Grove - Gas Sensor(MQ2). Retrieved from http://wiki.seeedstudio.com/Grove-Gas_Sensor-MQ2/
- [24] MQ2 Gas Sensor. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://components101.com/mq2-gas-sensor>
- [25] Cheng, Wei-Chung, Yu Hou, and Massoud Pedram. "Power minimization in a backlit TFT-LCD display by concurrent brightness and contrast scaling." In *Proceedings of the conference on Design, automation and test in Europe-Volume 1*, p. 10252. IEEE Computer Society, 2004.

- [26] Van De Witte, Peter, and Rifat Ata Mustafa Hikmet. "Transflective LCD display device comprising a patterned polarizer, display having the same, and method having the same." U.S. Patent 7,965,357, issued June 21, 2011.
- [27] 40x4 Character Display LCD, LCD Display 40x4. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.raystar-optronics.com/character-lcd-display-module/40x4-lcd.html>
- [28] Eckhardt, Wolfgang. "LCD display module." U.S. Patent Application 11/378,102, filed March 17, 2006.
- [29] Vieira, José António Barros, and Alexandre Manuel Mota. "Maximum power point tracker applied in batteries charging with PV panels." In Industrial Electronics, 2008. ISIE 2008. IEEE International Symposium on, pp. 202-207. IEEE, 2008
- [30] Gao, Lijun, Roger A. Dougal, Shengyi Liu, and Albena P. Iotova. "Parallel-connected solar PV system to address partial and rapidly fluctuating shadow conditions." IEEE Transactions on industrial Electronics 56, no. 5 (2009): 1548-1556.
- [31] Attia, Hussain A., Beza Negash Getu, Hasan Ghadban, and Ahmed K. Abu Mustafa. "Portable Solar Charger with Controlled Charging Current for Mobile Phone Devices." Int. J. of Thermal & Environmental Engineering 7, no. 1 (2014): 17-24.
- [32] Attia, Hussain A., Beza Negash Getu, Hasan Ghadban, and Ahmed K. Abu Mustafa. "Portable Solar Charger with Controlled Charging Current for Mobile Phone Devices." Int. J. of Thermal & Environmental Engineering 7, no. 1 (2014): 17-24.
- [33] Kuo, Yeong-Chau, Tsorng-Juu Liang, and Jiann-Fuh Chen. "Novel maximum-power-point-tracking controller for photovoltaic energy conversion system." IEEE transactions on industrial electronics 48, no. 3 (2001): 594-601.
- [34] Frannhagen, Bjorn G. "Battery pack that communicates intrinsic information over battery voltage terminals." U.S. Patent 5,990,659, issued November 23, 1999
- [35] Frannhagen, Bjorn G. "Battery pack that communicates intrinsic information over battery voltage terminals." U.S. Patent 5,990,659, issued November 23, 1999.
- [36] Sauer, Dirk Uwe, and Heinz Wenzl. "Comparison of different approaches for lifetime prediction of electrochemical systems—Using lead-acid batteries as example." Journal of Power sources 176, no. 2 (2008)